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PERFORMANCE OF PHARMA BRANDS, MOLECULES & COMPANIES IN THE EYE OF CHEMISTS

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ABSTRACT

Worldwide pharmaceutical companies are restructuring themselves; merger and acquisition have become the order of the day. There are more than 25000 pharmaceuticals firms, most of them are very small even larger ones have also not been conducting regular market surveys.

This study provides highly valuable information for determining their future marketing mix and business policies. There is (1) Large number of formulators and bulk drugs manufacturers for each molecule at lowest prices vis-à-vis rest of the world (2) Presence of a large number of propaganda firms. Therefore, a study of this kind to study the practices and priorities and to visualise likely changes in these is most imperative at this juncture.

It was found by the researcher that ratio of the products of the propaganda concerns is high in prescriptions these days. The prescriptions of the ethical companies are dominating in pharma market with seventy percentage market share. Researcher also found that almost twenty five market share was captured by propaganda companies which favours that ratio of the products of the propaganda concerns is high in prescriptions these days. This study also discussed that ratio of the products of the propaganda concerns is high in the prescriptions these days as the maximum number of respondents were in favour of the view that 41-50 percent portion of medicine were free from propaganda firms. Mostly chemists have responded positively to maintaining relations with doctor. Government practitioners are dominating in prescription. There are 20-40 percent of unnecessary drug in prescription by doctors. This research will certainly help pharmaceutical industry to work more on research and development area.

Keywords: Molecules, Drug, Brand, Pharmaceutical, Prescription, Medical practitioners

1. INTRODUCTION

The pharmaceutical industry plays a crucial role in the well-being of the country by formulating quality medicines. Increasing competition, a change market scenario and customer profile, increasing awareness amongst and users the Indian pharmaceutical industry is undergoing a metamorphosis. Worldwide pharmaceutical companies are restructuring themselves; merger and acquisition have become the order of the day. There are more than 25000 pharmaceuticals firms, most of them are very small even larger ones have also not been conducting regular market surveys. Therefore this study provides highly valuable information for determining their future marketing mix and business policies. There is (1) Large number of formulators and bulk drugs manufacturers for each molecule at lowest prices vis-à-vis rest of the world (2) Presence of a large number of propaganda firms. Therefore, a study of this kind to study the practices and priorities and to visualise likely changes in these is most imperative at this juncture. Alexander Tsai, "The study of Doctors, Pharmaceutical Companies differs in priorities (fwd)", www. <mailto:act2@po.cwru.edu>, Drug Directorate of

Health, Canada, et.al.; "The study of Physician Prescribing Practices", Doctor Libby Roughead, "The Study of Pharmaceutical Representative and Medical Practitioner Encounter: Implications for quality use of medicines", Project Timelines, Dr. R.K. Shrivastav, "A Study of New ethical dimensions in pharma marketing The Pharmaceutical Journal Vol 264 No. 7092 p 574 April 1000 Clinical, "A study of Prescribing Expensive Medicines", were some of the studies conducted to find out the opinion of chemists for pharma companies.

2. MATERIALS & METHODS

2.1 Objectives: The proposed study aims at the following:

- To Study the Performance of Brands and Molecules in the Eyes of Chemists
- To Study the Frequency (Ratio) of Propaganda and Ethical pharma Companies

2.2 Hypotheses: This study is primarily an **exploratory work**.

H₁ Criteria for selling a specified brand for particular chemical molecule in most of the cases is the corporate goodwill of the manufacturers.

H₂ Ratio of the products of the propaganda's concerns is high in the prescriptions.

2.3 Sources of Information: Primary Sources: Chemists

Table 1: Area Wise Distribution of the Chemists

Area	No. of Chemists	Percentage
Urban	50	50%
Semiurban	30	30%
Rural	20	20%
Total	100	100 %

Figure 1: Area Wise Distributions of the Chemists

From table 1 it can be observed that a majority 50 (50 percent) of chemists were from urban area, and 30 (30 percent) chemist respondents were from rural area, while 20 (20 percent) of chemist respondents were from semi urban areas. Interpretation reveals that a majority of 80 percent chemists respondents were from urban and semi urban areas while only 20 (20 percent) of chemists respondents were from rural areas.

3. RESULT & DISCUSSION

3.4 Drug Brand and Molecule Sales in the opinion of Chemist:

3.4.1 Performance of molecules brands and companies in the opinion of chemists.

3.4.2 Perceptions of chemists regarding companies and prescriptions

3.4.1 Performance of Molecules, Brands and Companies in the Opinion of Chemists: Chemists are the persons who sell the medicines to the buyers on the basis of physicians' prescription. They are very good source of information on performance of various brands available in the market and which brand is doing well in that particular area.

3.4.1(a) Frequency of Preference of Major Brands: Chemist opinion regarding brand of major salts having maximum sales from their counter has been studied.

Table 2: Most Preferred Brands of Major Salts

S. No.	Name of Brand	Name of Company	Average Score	Rank
1.	EES -400	Abott	1.95	XVIII
2.	Lanso-30	Acron	1.75	XXI
3.	Aero spar	Acron	1.95	XVIII
4.	Acnox	Acron	2.20	XVI
5.	Azithral	Alembic	1.80	XX
6.	Sparta	Alembic	2.30	XVI
7.	Nimegesic	Alembic	3.20	V
8.	Althrocin	Alembic	3.50	II
9.	Broadiclox	Alkem	1.85	XIX
10.	Omperaz	Alkem	2.60	XIII
11.	Alcipro	Alkem	2.80	X
12.	Throx	Alkem	2.10	VI
13.	Roxen	Aristo	2.40	XV
14.	Aristozyl	Aristo	2.80	X
15.	Combiflam	Aventis	3.60	I
16.	Beslofen	B.E,	1.80	XX
17.	Ampilox	Biochem	2.20	XVI
18.	Roxibest	Blue cross	2.20	XVI
19.	Cebran	Bluecross	2.60	XIII

20.	Symbiotic	Cadila	2.85	IX
21.	Acloc	Cadila	1.35	XXIII
22.	Synclar	Cipla	2.40	XV
23.	Amlopress-AT	Cipla	2.50	xrv
24.	Oflox	Cipla	2.60	XIII
25.	Ibugesic	Cipla	2.60	XIII
26.	Norflox	Cipla	2.80	X
27.	Amlopress	Cipla	2.90	VIII
28.	Cefadur	Cipla	2.90	VIII
29.	Novaclox	Cipla	3.10	VI
30.	Ciplox	Cipla	3.20	V
31.	Novamox	Cipla	3.60	I
32.	Nise	Dr.Reddy	3.40	III
33.	Omez	Dr.Reddy	3.50	II
34.	Ciprolet	Dr.Reddy	2.90	VIII
35.	Celex	Glaxo	2.60	XIII
36.	Betnesol	Glaxo	2.80	X
37.	Phexin	Glaxo	3.20	V
38.	Betnovate	Glaxo	3.60	I
39.	Candid	Glenmark	3.40	III
40.	Flucort	Grace well	2.60	XIII

It has been found from the table 2 research that respondents have ranked various brands as preferences among various groups of salts. Respondents have ranked Mox, Ciplox, Odoxil, Corvadil, Doxy-1, Omez, Rantac, Conibiilam, Diclovin Plus, Nise, Dexona, Candid and Betnovate etc. as first preference among brands of various salts in various groups. Respondents have ranked brands of various companies. Cipla has scored first, Ranbaxy has scored second, Torrent has scored third, Zydus Cadila has scored third, Alkem, Alembic and Glaxo all have scored fourth etc. Respondents have ranked one propaganda company Acron for fifth position.

It has been found that almost all respondent have said that all companies which wants to increase their sales, are providing various schemes on their product like some companies are providing ten percent and some twenty percent schemes, besides these pharma companies are also providing gifts and other items like diaries and calendars to chemists. It has been found that if respondents are getting something from that company then definitely they do their best to increase the sales of that particular company. In the research respondents were asked regarding efforts they are doing to increase the sales of any particular company. It has been found that for generic pharma companies from which they are getting good schemes, better profit margin, and respondents are putting their best efforts like counter pushing of the product and substitution of the product. It has been found

that from ethical pharma companies, respondents are getting ten to twenty percent schemes on whatever product respondents are not substituting that product of that particular company. It has been found that respondents, if getting adjustments on product by medical representative of any particular company then definitely they put their best efforts to increase the sales of that particular company.

It has been found that almost all respondents have named generic pharma companies for maximum profit margin. It has been found that respondents are getting a margin of sixty to seventy percent from generic pharma companies. It has been found that respondents are getting ten to twenty percent profit margins from ethical companies. There are some exceptions also from which respondents are getting more margins than other companies and if schemes on various products are included then respondents are getting more profit margins from ethical pharma companies. It has been found that propaganda pharma companies are not giving enough profit margins to respondents.

3.4.1(b) Maximum Sales Having Brands on Counter: There are some brands having maximum sales on chemist counter. There are various brands available in the market but some brands are doing very well as compare to other brands has been studied.

Table 3: Brands Giving Maximum Sales

S. No.	Name of Brand	Name of Company	No. of Respondents	Rank
1.	Althrocin	Alembic	8	IV
2.	Nimegesic	Alembic	3	IX
3.	Flexon	Aristo	7	V
4.	Megapen	Aristo	3	IX
5.	Allegra	Aventis	2	X
6.	Avil	Aventis	3	IX
7.	Combiflam	Aventis	9	III
8.	Daonil	Aventis	4	VIII
9.	Soframycin	Aventis	5	VII
10.	Cipcal	Cipla	1	XI
11.	Ciplox	Cipla	3	IX
12.	Novamox	Cipla	3	IX
13.	Nise	Dr.Reddy	5	VII
14.	Omez	Dr.Reddy	4	VIII
15.	Dexorange	FrankoIndia	3	IX
16.	Deriphyllin	German remedies	2	X
17.	Betnesol	Glaxo	2	X
18.	Betnovate	Glaxo	1	XI

19.	Zentac	Glaxo	4	VIII
20.	Llv-52	Himalayan	8	IV
21.	Cozy Plus	Indswift	3	IX
22.	Aten	Kopran	2	X
23.	Amlovas	Macleods	1	XI
24.	Voveran	Novartis	12	I
25.	Amlogard	Pfizer	1	XI
26.	Becosules Caps	Pfizer	12	I
27.	Corex	Pfizer	9	III
28.	Dolonex-DT	Pfizer	3	IX
29.	Protinex	Pfizer	4	VIII
30.	Cifran	Ranbaxy	3	IX
31.	Mox	Ranbaxy	10	II
32.	Crocin	Smithkline	4	VIII
33.	Quintor	Torrent	2	X
34.	Dynapar	Troikka	2	X
35.	Buscopan	TTK	1	XI
36.	Corvadil	Unichem	5	VII
37.	Trika	Unichem	7	V
38.	Metrogyl	Unique	2	X
39.	Betadine	Win	3	IX
40.	Dicloivin Plus	Wings	8	IV

From table 3 in the research respondents were asked regarding maximum sale of brands. Respondents have named various brands, some of them are very popular brands. It has been found that Voveran has scored first, Becosules Caps has scored first, and Mox has scored second. Combiflam has scored third, Folivite has scored fourth, Trika has scored fifth, and Flexon has also scored fifth, were among the brands having maximum sales from the respondent's counter. Other brands are also there ranked for maximum sales from the counter. It has been found that brand from various companies have been ranked by respondent. Respondents have ranked brands of some companies for more than one time. Pfizer and Aventis have scored first. Cipla and Glaxo has scored second, Wockliardt has scored third etc.

3.4.1(c) Maximum Sales Having Companies on Counter: Some companies doing very well on chemist counter. Major pharmaceutical firms as well as smaller pharma companies are performing well on counter. Chemists are also pushing products.

Table 4: Maximum Sales Having Companies: Chemists' Perception

S. No.	Name of Company	No. of Respondents	Percent	Rank
1.	Cipla Ethical / Generic	25	25%	I
2.	Sun	15	15%	II
3.	Acron	10	10%	in
4.	Intas	10	10%	in
5.	Pfizer	10	10%	in
6.	Aristo	5	5%	IV
7.	Alkem	5	5%	IV
8.	Glaxo	5	5%	IV
9.	Moko	5	5%	IV
10.	Morepen	5	5%	IV
11.	Cadila	5	5%	IV

Figure 2: Maximum Sales Having Companies Chemists' Perception

From the table 4 twenty five percent respondents have named Cipla ethical and generic as first company for maximum sales from their counter. Sun has scored second with fifteen percent respondents, Pfizer, and Intas has scored third with ten percent respondents, propoganda companies like Acron has scored third, and Moko has scored fourth. Respondents also named both propaganda pharmaceutical firms for maximum sales from their counter.

3.4.1(d) Most Popular Brands of Major Salts on Counter: There are some salts which are very common for practitioners. Practitioners are prescribing various brands of these salts. Some brands are very popular of these major salts.

Table 5: Most Popular Brands of Major Salts

Group 1 - Amoxicillin

S. No.	Name of Brand	Name of Company	Average Score	Rank
(a)	Mox	Ranbaxy	2.3	I
(b)	Wymox	Wyeth Lederle	1.6	II
(c)	Acmoz	Acron	0.95	III

Group 2 - Ciprofloxacin

S No.	Name of Brand	Name of Company	Average Score	Rank
(a)	Ciplox	Cipla	1.95	I
(b)	Alcipro	Alkem	1.40	II
(c)	Quintor	Torrent	1,30	III

Group 3 -Cefadroxil

S. No.	Name of Brand	Name of Company	Average Score	Rank
(a)	Cefadaur	Cipla	1.75	I
(b)	Odoxil	Lupin	1.55	II
(c)	Cefadrox	Aristo	1.2	III

Group 4 - Doxycycline

S. No.	Name of Brand	Name of Company	Average Score	Rank
(a)	Doxy- 1	U.S.V.	2.25	I
(b)	Doxypal-DR	Jagsonpal	1.55	II
(c)	Doxyric	Euphoric	1.3	III

Group 5 - Norfloxacin

S.No.	Name of Brand	Name of Company	Average Score	Rank
(a)	Norflox	Cipla	2.85	I
(b)	Norbactin	Ranbaxy	2.70	II
(c)	Urofloxx	Torrent	2.60	III

Group 6 - Amoxy + Cloxacillin

S. NO.	Name of Brand	Name of Company	Average Score	Rank
(a)	Symbiotic	Cadia	2.2	I
(b)	Novaclox	Cipla	2.1	II
(c)	Suprimox	Ranbaxy	1.75	III

Group 7 - Amolodipine

S. NO.	Name of Brand	Name of Company	Average Score	Rank
(a)	Corvadil	Unichem	2.5	I
(b)	Amlopress	Cipla	1.85	II
(c)	Amlovas	Macleods	1.60	III

Group 8 - Amlodipine + Atenolol

S. No.	Name of Brand	Name of Company	Average Score	Rank
(a)	Corvadil-A	Unichem	2.3	I
(b)	Amlovas-AT	Macleods	1.90	II
(c)	Amtas-AT	Intas	1.75	III

Group 9 – Lossartan Potassium

S. No.	Name of Brand	Name of Company	Average Score	Rank
(a)	Losacar	Cadila	2.2	I
(b)	Tozzar	Torrent	2.10	II
(c)	Losar	Unichem	1.95	III

Group 10 - Omeprazole

S. No.	Name of Brand	Name of Company	Average Score	Rank
(a)	Ornez	Dr. Reddy	2.60	I
(b)	Omepraz	Alkem	1.95	II
(c)	Ocid	Zydus Cadila	1.70	III

Group 11 -Pantoprazole

S. No.	Name of Brand	Name of Company	Average Score	Rank
(a)	Pantocid	Sun	2.40	I
(b)	Pantodac	Zydus Cadila	1.80	II
(c)	Pan-40	Alkem	1.20	III

Group 12 - Ibuprofen + Paracetamol

S. No.	Name of Brand	Name of Company	Average Score	Rank
(a)	Combiflam	Aventis	2.80	I
(b)	Flexon	Aristo	1.85	II
(c)	Be'stofen	Bio.E	1.60	III

Group 13 - Diclofenac + Paracetamol

S. No.	Name of Brand	Name of Company	Average Score	Rank
(a)	Diclovin-Plus	Wings	2.60	I
(b)	Combigesic D.P.	Bal Pharma	2.30	II
(c)	Dicloran-A	Lekar	1.75	III

It has been found from table 5 of the research that respondents have named various brands which are most popular and have highest sales from their counter. Mox of Ranbaxy has scored first in-group one. Ciplox of Cipla has scored first in group two. Cefadur of Cipla has scored first in-group three. Doxy-1 of USV has scored first in fourth groups, Norflox of Cipla has secured first in group five, and Symbiotic of Cadila has scored first in group six. Corvadil of Unichem has scored first in group seven Corvadil -A of Unichem has scored first in group eight, Losacar of Cadila has scored first in group nine, Omez of Dr.Reddy has scored first in group ten, and Pantocid of Sun has scored first in group eleven.

Combiflam of Aventis has scored first in group twelve. Diclovin plus of Wings pharma has scored first in group thirteen, Dexona of Zydus cadila has scored first in group fourteen and Betnovate of Glaxo has scored first in group fifteen for most popular and highest sales having brands. It has been found that Cipla has scored as first Preference Company.

It has been found from this research that respondents have ranked Cipla for number one company, whose brands they prefer most. Unichem, Cadila, Glaxo, Torrent, Alkem, and Aristo etc. are the other companies' respondents preferring most.

3.4.2 Perception of Chemists Regarding Companies and Prescriptions: Chemists have exact information regarding which type of company is dominating in prescriptions whether it is ethical, propaganda or generic.

3.4.2(a) Nature of Company Dominating in Prescriptions:

Table 6: Company Dominating in Prescriptions Chemists' Perception

S. No.	Type of Company	No of Respondents	Percent	Rank
1.	Ethical	70	70%	I
2.	Propaganda	25	25%	II
3.	Generic	5	5%	III

Figure 3: Companies Dominating in Prescriptions Chemists'

From table 6 in this research respondent were asked regarding the type of company dominating in prescription by doctors, *to test the hypothesis that the ratio of the products of the propaganda concerns is high in the prescriptions these days, a direct question was asked to the chemists on companies dominating in prescriptions. Twenty five percent of respondents were in favour of above hypothesis. The above ratio*

occupied by the propaganda firm is very high as far as pharma market is concerned. Seventy-percent respondents have named ethical pharma companies for dominating in prescription by doctors. It has been found that generic pharma companies are not dominating in prescription by doctors. Only five percent of respondents have named generic pharma companies for domination in prescription. Thus the second hypothesis is largely proved that the ratio of propaganda products is high in prescription these days.

3.4.2(b) Brands being Prescribed and their Earlier Ones: There are some brands very popular having maximum sales at present, earlier there were some other brands of other companies were doing well. This may be because of various reasons.

Table 7: Brands Currently Prescribed and their Earlier Ones

S. No.	Currently	Name of Company	5 years ago	Name of Company	10 years ago	Name of Company
1	Alcipro	Alkem	Ciprobid	Cadila	Cifran	Ranbaxy
2	Althrocin	Alembic	Etomin	Sun	Eltocin	Ipca
3	Zenflox	Mankind	Tarivid	Aventis	Zanocin	Ranbaxy
4	Acrox	Acron	Mox	Ranbaxy	Wymox	Wyeth
5	Sparlox	Sun	Sparta	Alembic	Scat	Cadila

It has been found from the table 7 from this research that respondents have named several brands which are at present top selling brands like Alcipro, Althrocin, Zenflox, Acrox, Sparlox, etc., Earlier there were other brands as top brands like five years ago Ciprobid and ten years ago Cifran was doing very well. Also in case of Ofloxacin brands earlier Tarivid and Zanocin were doing very well but currently other companies brand like Zenflox of Mankind is doing well, this may be because of cost of the brand and several other factors.

3.4.2(c) Chemist Liaison with Practitioners: Chemist and practitioners relations are very important from various points of views. In this section of the chapter chemists have given their opinion regarding their relation with the practitioners. Chemists have different opinion about maintaining liaison with the doctor.

Table 8: Maintaining Liaison with Practitioners

S.No.	Response	No. of Respondents	Percent	Rank
1	Positive	70	70%	I
2	Negative	30	30%	II

Figure 4: Maintaining Liaisons with Practitioners

It has been found from the table 8 that when respondents were asked regarding their liaison with doctors, most of the respondents (seventy-percent) responded positively for maintaining liaison with doctors. Out of all respondents seventy percent of them believe in maintaining positive relation with doctors. Thirty percent of respondents have responded negatively.

3.4.2(d) Type of Doctors who's Prescription Comes to Counter: Chemists are the person who has information regarding type of doctors whose prescriptions are coming to their counter has been studied in this section.

Table 9: Prescriptions to Counter Chemists' perception

S. No.	Category	No. of Respondents	Percent	Rank
1	Government Practitioners	60	60%	I
2	Private Practitioners	30	30%	II
3	General Practitioners	10	10%	III

Figure 5: Prescriptions to Counter Chemists' perception

From the table 9 in the research respondents were asked regarding type of doctors whose prescription comes to their counter. Here type of doctors means whether the doctor is government practitioners, private practitioners or general practitioners. It has been found from the research that there are more number of government practitioners (sixty percent) in the research area, private practitioners are also there but they are less in numbers(thirty percent).General practitioners were only ten percent includes Ayurvedic, and Homeopathic etc.

3.4.2(e) Unnecessary Drugs in Prescriptions by Practitioners: There are lot of unnecessary drugs in prescriptions by doctors because of various reasons has been already studied in earlier chapters. Chemists have information on how many unnecessary drugs in the prescriptions by doctors. It has been studied in this section.

In this research from the table 10 respondents were asked regarding percent of unnecessary drugs in prescription by doctors. It has been found from this research that a major part of respondents have said that there are 31-40 percent which has scored first, unnecessary drugs in prescription by doctors. 21-30 percent has scored second, in unnecessary drug category and 41-50 percent has scored third in unnecessary drugs category. 51-60 percent category has scored fourth. Any respondents have not taken 60-100 percent category of unnecessary drugs into account.

Table 10: Unnecessary Drugs in Prescriptions

S. No.	Percent of Drugs	Average Score	Rank
1.	31-40	1.60	I
2.	21-30	0.90	II
3.	41-50	0.50	III
4.	51-60	0.30	IV
5.	11-20	0.06	V
6.	0-10	0.05	VI
7.	61-70	0.00	VII
8.	71-80	0.00	VII
9.	81-90	0.00	VII
10.	91-100	0.00	VII

3.4.2(f) Prescriptions Free From Propaganda Concern by Practitioners: Chemists have information on medicines free from propaganda firms in prescriptions by doctors. It has been studied in this section. Key findings are being presented hereunder.

Table 11: Prescription Free From Propaganda Concern

S. No.	Percent of Prescriptions	Average Score	Rank
1.	41-50	1.6	I
2.	51-60	0.75	II
3.	31-40	0.6	III
4.	21-30	0.5	IV
5.	61-70	0.35	V
6.	11-20	0.1	VI
7.	0-10	0.05	VII
8.	71-80	0.00	VIII
9.	81-90	0.00	VIII
10.	91-100	0.00	VIII

From table 11: a disguised question on medicines free from propaganda concerns was also framed to collect the exact information about the share of propaganda firms in the prescriptions to test the hypothesis that the ratio of the products of the propaganda concerns is high in the prescriptions these days. The results of table 6.10 show that maximum number of respondents was in favour of the view that 41-50 percent of prescriptions are free from propaganda concerns. It means that the rest 50 percent portion was of propaganda concerns the above view has achieved first ranked with maximum average score. It has been found that 51-60 percent and 31-40 percent has scored second and third respectively. Any respondents have not taken 70-100 percent category into account. Thus the fourth hypothesis is again proved.

3.4.2 (f) Daily Propaganda Prescriptions to Counter: In this section of the chapter chemist's opinion about daily propaganda prescriptions to their counter has been discussed. Nowadays emergence of propaganda firms in the market is increasing rapidly. Key findings are being presented hereunder.

Table 12: Daily Propaganda Prescriptions to Counter

S. No.	Prescriptions	No. of Respondents	Percent	Rank
1	11-15	40	40%	I
2	16-20	30	30%	II
3	6-10	20	20%	III
4	0-5	10	10%	IV

In this research from table 12 when respondents were asked regarding how many propaganda prescriptions daily come to their counter. It has been found that from this research that major part of respondents have said that 11-15 (forty-percent) prescriptions are of propaganda firms daily coming to their counters. The results of table 12 daily propaganda prescriptions to counter are also favour the fourth hypothesis that the ratio of the product of the propaganda concerns is high in prescriptions these days.

4. CONCLUSION

- Chemists have ranked various brands as preference among group of salts. Mostly brand belongs to Cipla, Ranbaxy, Torrent, Cadila, Alkem, Alembic and Glaxo etc. major pharma companies.
- Among maximum selling brands Voveran of Novartis, Becosule Caps of Pfizer, Mox of Ranbaxy, Corex of Pfizer, Combiflam of Aventies have scored over others.
- Cipla ethical and generic has scored first. Sun, Intas, Pfizer, Cadila, Morepen were other companies giving maximum sales on counter. Apart from ethical firms propaganda concerns like Acron and Moko were also there giving maximum sales on counter.
- In major salts category brands of Cipla company has achieved maximum sales followed by brands of Glaxo, Aventies, Dr. Reddy, Unichem, Cadila, USV etc.
- The prescriptions of the ethical companies are dominating in pharma market with seventy percentage market share. As the table 6 shows that twenty five market share was captured by propaganda companies which favours **the hypothesis that ratio of the products of the propaganda concerns is high in prescriptions these days.**
- The results of table 11 also favours the **hypothesis that ratio of the products of the propaganda concerns is high in the prescriptions** these days as the maximum number of respondents were in favour of the view that 41-50 percent portion of medicine were free from propaganda firms.
- Mostly chemists have responded positively to maintaining relations with doctor. Government practitioners are dominating in prescription. There are 20-40 percent of unnecessary drug in prescription by doctors.

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